

DYES DERIVED FROM ACENAPHTHENEQUINONE. PART VII. 2-(5-CHLORO)-THIONAPHTHENE-ACENAPHTHYLENE- INDIGOS.

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5-Chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene has been condensed with acenaphthenequinone and a few of its derivatives and also phenanthraquinone. The newly prepared 5-chloro-indigoid vat dyes, described here, are found to be distinctly deeper than the corresponding 5-methyl compounds already studied.

In a series of papers, a systematic and detailed study has been made of the influence of the methyl group on the colour of 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthyleneindigos (Ciba Scarlet G and its derivatives), 3-indole-2'-thionaphtheneindigos (Thioindigo Scarlet R and its derivatives), 2-thionaphthene-1'-aceanthryleneindigo, bis-2-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo, and benzylidene-2-thionaphthenes, according as it is present in the 4-, 5-, or 6-position of the thionaphthene nucleus of the molecule, *i.e.*, in the *ortho*, *meta*, and *para* position with reference to the carboxyl group (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 679; 1936, **13**, 94; 1938, **15**, 20; Guha and Basu-Maillick, *ibid.*, 1934, **11**, 395; Guha, *ibid.*, 1937, **14**, 240; 1938, **15**, 501; 1935, **12**, 659; 1937, **14**, 709; 1938, **15**, 359; *cf.* Auwers and Arndt, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 541; Friedländer, *Monatsh*, 1909, **30**, 347).

The colour, dyeing properties and absorption spectra revealed the fact that in each of the series mentioned above, the 5-methyl derivative is the deepest in shade, the second is the parent compound, next comes the 4-methyl compound and last is the 6-methyl dye. From the present state of our knowledge regarding colour and chemical constitution it is difficult to explain why the introduction of the methyl group in the 4- and 6-position should lighten the colour of the parent substances, and deeper shades should be obtained when the same group occupies the 5-position. It was felt that further work is necessary on the subject and the effect of the introduction of other atoms or groups in different positions must be determined before it is possible to put forward any comprehensive generalisation.

With this object in view, it was decided to make a systematic study of the influence of the position of the chlorine atom, precisely in the same manner as has been already done in the case of the methyl group in the acenaphthenequinone, isatin, aceanthrenequinone, conjugated-indigo analogues and thioindigenide series (Guha, *loc. cit.*). For this purpose

5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (D. R. P. 224567, Friedländer, 10, 474; Auwers and Thies, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 2285) was condensed with acenaphthenequinone, and its 3-chloro-, 3-bromo-, and 1-methoxy derivatives, and the corresponding indigoid vat dyes obtained.

These newly prepared dyes are soluble in pyridine and nitrobenzene and sparingly soluble in alcohol. The parent compound as well as its chloro and bromo derivatives dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid giving deep green solutions, but the methoxy derivative, when treated similarly, produces a blue solution. From sulphuric acid solutions, on the addition of water, the dyes are reprecipitated unchanged in a finely divided state, suitable for dyeing on wool from an acid bath. When heated strongly above 312°, they melt and quickly volatilise evolving coloured vapours of the respective substances. The dyeing shades on wool from a dilute sulphuric acid bath and on cotton from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat, develop well, except in the case of the methoxy derivative where full shades are not obtained. A considerable amount of difficulty has been experienced in reducing it in the vat. The violet-red alkaline vat obtained in this case, after repeated trial, turns into pink by air oxidation [*cf.* 2-thionaphthene-8'(1'-methoxy)-acenaphthyleneindigo, its 4-, 5- and 6-methyl derivatives; 2:3-naphthathionaphene-8'-(1'-methoxy)acenaphthyleneindigo, Staudinger, Goldstein and Schlenker, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 342; Guha, *loc. cit.*].

Lastly, another indigoid dye in the phenanthraquinone series 2-(5-chloro)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthreneindigo was prepared with the object of comparing its dyeing properties with those of 2-(5-chloro)-thionaphtheneacenaphthyleneindigo. The dark chocolate coloured substance dyes wool in brown shades from an acid bath and imparts a faint brown colour to cotton from a yellow alkaline vat.

The 5-chloro dyes, described in this paper, produce on cotton shades which are distinctly deeper than those obtained from the corresponding 5-methyl compounds (Guha, Guha and Basu-Mallick., *loc. cit.*). A comparative statement of the shades from some of them is tabulated below.

Compounds	Shades on cotton.
A = Acenaphthylene-indigo.	T = Thionaphthene.
2-(5-Chloro)-T-A.	Dark red
2-(5-Me)-thionaphthene-A.	Scarlet red
2-(5-Chloro)-T-8' (3'-chloro) A	Dark red.
2-(5-Me)-T-8' (3'-chloro)-A.	Scarlet red.
2-(5-Chloro)-T-8' (3'-bromo)-A.	Dark red.
2-(5-Me)-T-8' (3'-bromo)-A.	Scarlet red.
2-(5-Chloro)-T-8' (1'-methoxy)-A.	Pink.
2-(5-Me)-T-8' (1'-methoxy)-A.	Pink.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

2-(5-Chloro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthyleneindigo.

It separated as light violet-red well-defined needles from a solution of acenaphthenequinone (0.364 g.) and 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.368 g.) in glacial acetic acid (70 c.c.) and 4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid on boiling the mixture for 15 minutes. The dye (0.492 g.) crystallised from xylene in foliated hair-like dark red needles. It is soluble in xylene, difficultly soluble in amyl alcohol, moderately soluble in chloroform and benzene; sparingly soluble in acetic acid. The dyeing shade on wool is dark red from an acid bath; cotton is also dyed in the same colour from an alkaline deep violet vat. (Found: Cl, 10.48. $C_{20}H_9O_2ClS$ requires Cl, 10.18 per cent).

2-(5-Chloro)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro)-acenaphthyleneindigo was obtained by heating 3-chloroacenaphthenequinone (0.433 g.) and 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.369 g.) in 55 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 6 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 15 minutes, as fine red needles which when dried become brownish red. The product (0.451 g.) was crystallised from pyridine when it came down in the form of long needles. It dyes wool in brownish red shades from an acid bath and cotton in dark red shades from an alkaline deep violet-blue vat. It resembles the parent compound in solubility. (Found: Cl, 18.78. $C_{20}H_8O_2Cl_2S$ requires Cl, 18.56 per cent).

2-(5-Chloro)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-acenaphthyleneindigo was prepared in the same way as the preceding compound from 3-bromoacenaphthenequinone (0.398 g.) and 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.282 g.) in 35 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 3 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The red crystalline precipitate which on drying became brownish red (0.422 g.) was crystallised from pyridine. It formed thread like needles. It resembles the chloro compound in other properties. (Found: S, 7.29. $C_{20}H_8O_2BrClS$ requires S, 7.48 per cent).

2-(5-Chloro)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-acenaphthyleneindigo separated from β -methoxyacenaphthenequinone (0.636 g.) and 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.5535 g.) in 100 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 5 c.c.

of concentrated hydrochloric acid when boiled for 25-30 minutes as a dark red crystalline precipitate. The dye (0.283 g.) when crystallised from pyridine formed needle-shaped crystals. It is difficultly soluble in xylene, chloroform, moderately soluble in acetic acid. It dyes wool in light red shades. (Found : Cl, 9.74. $C_{21}H_{11}O_3ClS$ requires Cl, 9.37 per cent).

2-(5-Chloro)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthreneindigo.

The hot solution of phenanthraquinone (0.624 g.) and 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.5535 g.) in glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) was treated with 4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid and shaken, when a crystalline mass separated. Glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) was added and the solution boiled for 20 minutes. The dye (0.264 g.) was collected, washed with acetic acid, hot water and crystallised from pyridine in dark chocolate needles. It is soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene, aniline; difficultly soluble in xylene, sparingly soluble in toluene, acetic acid and alcohol. (Found : Cl, 9.71. $C_{22}H_{11}O_2ClS$ requires Cl, 9.47 per cent)

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